

AGRICULTURAL SCIENCES

SEASONAL PRICE VOLATILITY FOR MAIZE IN KADUNA AND KATSINA STATE, NIGERIA

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Abstract

This study assessed the seasonal price volatility of maize prices in Katsina and Kaduna state in 2023 and 2024. Market prices for maize were collected in 12 rural markets from the selected markets in Kaduna and Katsina state. Descriptive statistics; percentages, mean, standard deviation and coefficient of variation were used to analyse the data. The result shows different seasonal patterns where the postharvest prices decreased followed by increase during the months of May to August. There was near double prices increase in 2024 compared to 2023, with Kaduna state markets showing a 104.2% increase while, Katsina state markets showed a 103.7 to 106.2% increase. Despite inflationary pressures, volatility in prices decreased showing a coefficient of variation in the two years compared with minimum of 30% and 40% maximum in 2023, and from 20% minimum to 25% maximum in 2024 for Kaduna and from 23% minimum to 26% maximum in 2023 and from 17% minimum and 22% maximum in 2024 for Katsina state. Saminaka market in Kaduna state and Tsiga market in Katsina state showed better price stability, while Tudun saibu market in Kaduna state and Bakori market in Katsina state showed higher volatility. The study recommended the need for improve storage facilities, establish, sensitize and encourage farmers to use electronic warehouse receipt system, enhanced market information system, targeted policy intended policy interventions to stabilize prices, and reduce postharvest losses to enhance food security in line the sustainable development goal of ending hunger, achieving food security, improving nutrition and promoting sustainable agriculture (SDG 2).

Keywords: Maize, price volatility, season, rural market, seasonal trends.

1.0 INTRODUCTION

Maize is an important grain to Nigeria food and agribusiness sector. It serves as staple for human, live-stock feed production. It is in high demand as key ingredient for poultry and other industries (Wossen *et al.*, 2023). The major factors influencing agricultural commodity price movements in the rural markets are supply shocks, storage behaviour and trade policies. Maize prices are highly volatile, seasonal and show a postharvest decline in Nigeria (Gilbert, Christiaensen & Kaminski, 2017; Zalkuwi, Joshua, Faci & Kayam, 2024).

One of the factors contributing to price volatility is postharvest loss, which remains a challenge in Nigeria's agricultural sector. Grains produced is lost annually due to inefficiencies in harvest practices, storage and transportation issues. These losses reduce marketable surplus, contributing to price increase during Preharvest season typically in the month of May to end of August leading to depressing farm gate prices postharvest usually in the month of October to December yearly.

Over the years government have made some effort through execution of some projects such as the silo project and growth enhancement scheme under the Agricultural Transformation Agenda (ATA). However, the adoption of postharvest loss reduction techniques such as hermetic storage bags, remains low among the small-holder farmers due to high cost and limited extension

services. Also, the Nigerian Store Products Research Institute (NSPRI) has promoted metal silos and drying technologies, but scalability is constrained by financial limitation and affordability to farmers, awareness and institutional support (Federal Ministry of Agriculture and Rural Development [FMARD], 2011; World Bank, 2014; Oyewole *et al.*, 2018).

With all these, farmers and traders still face significant challenges mainly due to price fluctuation caused by seasonality in production and inadequate storage facilities and fragmented market leading to price fluctuation. Reducing postharvest losses could stabilize prices and enhance food security and this goal aligned with SDG 2, "Zero Hunger", emphasizing the need for integrated policies addressing storage, market access, and farmer education.

This study addresses three key questions including the following:

- i. what are the seasonal price trends for maize in Kaduna and Katsina state?
- ii. which of the rural maize markets exhibits higher price volatility?
- iii. What was the seasonal price variability between 2023 and 2024 in the study area?

2.0 MATERIALS AND METHODS

2.1 The Study Area

The study was carried out in selected rural markets in Kaduna and Katsina States in the northwestern part

of Nigeria. Kaduna State lies between latitude 9°30'N and 11° 30'N and longitude 7°00'E and 8° 30'E, while Katsina State was situated at between latitude 11°30'N and 30° 20'N and longitude 6°50'E and 9° 20'E. The region falls within the Sudan Savannah agroecological zone, characterized by a tropical climate with distinct wet and dry seasons. The annual rainfall ranges between 800 mm and 1,200 mm, with temperatures varying from 25°C to 35°C.

Kaduna state, market selected for the study were Anchau, Makarfi, Tudun Saibu, Ikara, Giwa, Saminaka, and Pambegua, while Katsina State, market selected for the study were Bakori, Dandume, Jabiri (Funtua), Faskari and Tsiga. These rural markets serve as major hub for agricultural trade, dealing in crops such as maize, millet, sorghum, cowpeas, and the rest including livestock.

Fig. 1.: Map of Nigeria showing the study area

The selection of these markets was based on their economic significance, and representation of the rural trade for maize in the northwestern Nigeria.

2.2 Methodology

Farm gate market prices for maize were collected for 2 years period, 2023 and 2024 (January - December)

from a total of 12 major rural markets across the 2 states; Kaduna and Katsina state on market days bases which were either weekly or on five days basis from the different markets in the study. Descriptive statistics; mean, percentage, standard deviation and coefficient of variation was used to analyse the data.

Table 1

List of selected markets for the study.

S/N	State	Names of markets
1.	Kaduna	1. Anchau
		2. Makarfi
		3. Tudun Saibu
		4. Ikara
		5. Giwa
		6. Saminaka
		7. Pambegua
2.	Katsina	1. Bakori
		2. Dandume
		3. Jabiri (Funtua)
		4. Faskari
		5. Tsiga

3.0 RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

3.1 Seasonal Price Trends

3.2 Kaduna State Price Movement 2023

The result in table 2. below shows, the average monthly maize price trends across selected rural markets in Kaduna State (Anchau, Makarfi, Tudun Saibu, Ikara, Giwa, Saminaka, and Pambegua). The result

shows predictable seasonal patterns and important market specific variations, seasonal fluctuations, and important implications for food security. This is in line with similar study in Nigeria's maize market that found similar cyclical behaviour, where prices tend to decline postharvest and rise during the dry season before harvest season (Liverpool-Tasie *et al.*, 2017; Gilbert *et al.*, 2017).

Table 2

Result of average monthly price of maize per market in Kaduna state in 2023

Months	Anchau (₦/kg)	Makarfi (₦/kg)	Tudun Saibu (₦/kg)	Ikara (₦/kg)	Giwa (₦/kg)	Saminaka (₦/kg)	Pambegua (₦/kg)
Jan.	205.92	210.00	200.99	205.00	208.33	193.17	205.07
Feb.	189.47	215.00	180.44	208.00	208.00	186.84	193.13
Mar.	177.59	159.00	174.12	196.81	209.00	188.58	199.63
Apr.	213.00	211.00	207.18	210.53	197.00	204.21	214.99
May	248.42	300.00	238.82	234.04	218.00	240.76	233.01
Jun.	285.26	302.69	307.37	289.47	300.00	281.21	279.96
Jul.	360.61	370.00	440.00	372.34	370.00	369.77	353.98
Aug.	493.38	455.00	515.42	465.25	493.60	470.14	482.48
Sep.	539.06	537.00	438.67	471.25	496.67	465.35	455.70
Oct.	361.42	353.54	232.32	281.75	315.63	281.59	308.14
Nov.	342.71	359.50	356.67	350.17	358.42	330.88	327.53
Dec.	384.89	397.49	402.78	388.22	416.52	383.40	358.16
Average	330.67	334.80	312.82	306.15	331.04	298.07	301.66

Source: Survey Data, 2025

The result as presented in Table 2 for Tudun Saibu market in 2023 showed price change between ₦174 - ₦515/kg, this could be due to infrastructure limitations. In contrast to Saminaka market with relatively stable price of ₦186 - ₦470/kg for the year. This could be due to better market organization and storage facility. Makarfi market total average for the year was ₦334.80/kg and Anchau was ₦330.67/kg, these recorded the highest mean prices, while Saminaka market was the least with ₦298.07/kg and was followed by Ikara ₦306.15/kg.

However, the persistent price differentials indicate that transaction costs, nature of road and storage facility availability, still create meaningful market segmentation (Abdulai, 2000; Liverpool-Tasie *et al.*, 2017). There was, however, a price rise to ₦539/kg in September, showing a substantial opportunity for profitable storage and arbitrage investments.

There was a consistent seasonal pattern indicating the predictive price information could significantly benefit market participants. Enhance market information services could also assist farmers optimize selling time. The higher volatility in Tudun Saibu market highlight the need for continued investment in rural transportation infrastructure to improve market integration (Abate *et al.*, 2020).

3.3 Kaduna State Price Movement 2024

The result for 2024 season of maize prices showed an upward shift in price levels for the year. The average annual prices increased across the markets with Makarfi recording the highest average at ₦699.25/kg. This suggests an inflationary surge exceeding previous seasonal fluctuations and which aligns maize market price where inflationary pressures have amplified staple grain prices.

Table 3

Result of average monthly price of maize per market in Kaduna state in 2024

Months	Anchau (₦/kg)	Makarfi (₦/kg)	Tudun Saibu (₦/kg)	Ikara (₦/kg)	Giwa (₦/kg)	Saminaka (₦/kg)	Pambegua (₦/kg)
Jan	496.13	518.43	484.19	492.35	492.42	475.29	462.96
Feb	542.15	558.17	547.93	556.83	518.27	523.93	528.64
Mar	555.56	573.48	560.97	573.40	562.03	535.86	532.42
Apr	558.15	566.33	533.18	551.87	542.45	505.95	513.62
May	620.43	628.71	588.75	623.70	600.66	592.49	555.50
Jun	850.00	818.50	814.33	909.25	814.50	753.62	761.34
Jul	893.91	862.26	831.61	947.51	838.33	797.69	819.29
Aug	855.90	896.34	873.22	940.49	888.80	801.37	794.83
Sep	832.59	852.26	810.90	884.29	932.29	708.09	713.74
Oct	639.07	657.61	637.08	675.64	663.27	492.14	570.53
Nov	648.67	690.43	634.00	662.22	550.00	561.48	576.60
Dec	639.47	646.51	571.54	677.30	613.86	548.94	606.38
Average	675.26	699.25	652.49	697.04	648.97	611.88	618.00

Source: Survey Data, 2025

These findings corroborate with the projection of AFEX, that projected maize prices would rise significantly in 2024 due to higher input costs and other supply chain pressures (AFEX, 2024). The market differentiation became more pronounced in 2024, price dispersion between markets increasing by about 18% compared to 2023 levels. This could be an indication for transportation cost and local market structure playing important role in price formation with volatility in Ikara market of ₦492 to ₦947/kg.

The 2024 maize price result shows complexity of a food system under stress and policy changes. According to a study by Zalkuwi *et al.* (2024), maize markets exhibited high price instability across states from 2017 - 2023, with considerable month to month fluctuations. While familiar season patterns were seen in agribusiness market environment, it challenges the existing models and policy frameworks. This shows the need for both immediate interventions to ensure food access and long term strategies to rebuild market resilience.

Figure 2: Result of Kaduna state price movement 2023 vis-a-vis 2024

The market pattern showed that, Makarfi market recorded the highest market price in both of the years increasing from ₦334.80/kg in 2023 to ₦699.25/kg in 2024 (108.9% increase). Similarly, Saminaka was the lowest with a rise from ₦298.07/kg to ₦611.88/kg (105.3% increase).

The 2023 result showed a relatively smooth parabolic curve with a peak in September, while the 2024 trend exhibits more abrupt transition. There was a post-harvest decline in October to December, but it was less in 2024 compared to 2023. This may be due to stronger

3.4 Comparing Kaduna State Price between 2023 and 2024

Kaduna state market shows transformations in dynamics between 2023 and 2024, which showed that, a trend of significant inflationary pressures and evolving market behaviour. The result of the 2023 and 2024 season as shown in Figure 2 showed that, there was a close to double increase in maize prices across the market with an average surge from ₦298 to ₦335/kg in 2023 to a range of ₦612 to ₦699/kg in 2024. This result represents an average increase of 104.2% across all markets showing inflationary pressures and suggests fundamental changes. The price increases threaten price vulnerable populations out of staple food markets, while the seasonal patterns may disrupt traditional risk management strategies employed by both producers and consumers. The graph below showed the upward shift with the entire 2024 price maintaining a consistently higher position than 2023 level annual cycle.

demand or change in trader expectations about future price movements (Zalkuwi *et al.*, 2024; AFEX, 2024).

3.5 Katsina State Price Movement 2023

The monthly price fluctuation for Katsina across the 5 rural markets; Bakori, Dandume, Jabiri (Funtua), Faskari, and Tsiga markets in 2023 showed a pattern as seen in Table 4. and discussed below with a fairly predictable patterns showing a potential for establishing price forecasting systems to inform farmers on marketing decisions.

Table 4

Result of average monthly price of maize per market in Katsina State in 2023						
Months	Bakori (₦/kg)	Dandume (₦/kg)	Jabiri (Funtua) (₦/kg)	Faskari (₦/kg)	Tsiga (₦/kg)	
January	202.82	208.24	196.02	200.00	205.88	
February	206.00	202.10	200.98	205.88	205.88	
March	205.26	214.29	207.00	206.00	206.70	
April	215.69	226.94	208.00	207.00	208.00	
May	240.20	256.96	257.90	262.53	258.94	
June	304.44	306.63	306.17	313.11	315.00	
July	323.53	390.72	370.57	428.33	315.00	
August	565.00	523.04	490.20	570.71	503.57	
September	605.00	367.81	401.99	388.35	411.76	
October	302.32	332.24	326.18	339.73	334.00	
November	357.90	377.04	372.52	354.43	367.61	
December	391.42	420.00	389.98	365.86	412.50	
Average	327.20	329.65	353.94	340.30	303.93	

Source: Survey Data, 2025

The prices remained fairly stable between ₦196 - ₦227/kg during the 2023 period, which shows adequate market supplies following the harvest. This was notable in Jabiri (Funtua) market, which maintained the lowest price of ₦196 - ₦208/kg which suggest efficient market function during surplus periods. However, price began rising steadily to an average range of ₦240 - ₦315/kg as stocks diminished, with all markets showing similar upward movement in Katsina State. The 30 - 35% increase during this period indicates inventory depletion across the States, consistent with broader findings on seasonal post-harvest price surges in Nigerian grain markets (Gilbert *et al.*, 2017). These reached an annual maximum of an average range of ₦323 - ₦605/kg with a significant variation, in Bakori market a price of ₦605/kg in September, Faskari market of ₦570.71/kg in August, Dandume market ₦523.04/kg in August The 2.8 - 3.1 percent increase from post-harvest levels exceeds typical seasonal variations observed in more integrated markets, suggesting potential supply chain constraints.

The price decline from an average range of ₦302 - ₦420/kg but remain elevated compared to beginning of year indicating either strong underlying demand or staggered market entry of new production. Faskari market showed most volatile prices ranging from ₦200 to ₦570.71/kg while, Tsiga showed relatively stable range of ₦205.88 to ₦503.57/kg for the year. These variations may be due to differences in market infrastructure

quality, trade concentration, transportation access, storage facility among others (Zalkuwi *et al.*, 2024).

Funtua market recorded the highest mean price of ₦353.94/kg while Tsiga was ₦303.93/kg. These differences indicated variation in local demand such as proximity to urban centre of Funtua compared to Tsiga market, differences in market fees and transportation cost. Also, Bakori market's high price of an average of ₦605/kg in September, showed a localized supply disruption, transportation bottlenecks, inadequate storage capacity and market information failure.

The rise in price at this period indicated profitable storage investment opportunity. This call for targeted inventions such as community storage facilities, hermetic storage technology adoption and warehouse receipt system. There was however, price differentials of up to ₦237/kg between markets in September. This suggests potential gains from improved market information system to facilitate arbitrage. The inter-market price differences highlight the need for improved rural transportation network to enhance market integration (AFEX, 2024).

3.6 Katsina State Price Movement 2024

The result for 2024 maize price in Katsina showed a significant rise in price of maize. The average annual maize price in 2024 ranged from ₦636.89/kg in Faskari to ₦679.70/kg in Dandume, representing a near doubling compared to the 2023 averages of ₦303.93 - ₦353.94/kg.

Table 5

Result of average monthly price of maize per market in Katsina state in 2024						
Months	Bakori (₦/kg)	Dandume (₦/kg)	Jabiri (Funtua) (₦/kg)	Faskari (₦/kg)	Tsiga (₦/kg)	
January	475.31	500.81	493.21	482.27	511.67	
February	530.44	551.21	537.30	525.30	558.89	
March	552.48	582.84	568.99	563.94	592.46	
April	564.76	532.40	553.96	535.38	585.11	
May	633.62	621.76	644.20	605.31	626.45	
June	828.62	849.35	860.25	603.16	710.00	
July	854.29	874.06	877.32	830.78	784.31	
August	864.37	857.67	899.81	831.00	880.00	
September	825.91	799.00	807.73	780.18	827.06	
October	570.23	667.24	622.84	618.00	664.18	
November	630.73	635.55	625.02	593.02	627.26	
December	612.48	618.00	618.00	494.74	590.00	
Average	666.53	679.70	672.51	636.89	653.42	

Source: Survey Data, 2025

This translates into 95 - 110% increase across the five rural markets, consistent with national level food inflation trends where cereal prices rose sharply during 2024 (Relief Web, 2024). The result of 2024 showed an upward shift in price level throughout the annual cycle with an average price doubled from 2023 level across all markets. This could make consumers face increased food insecurity risks as staple affordability declines and farmers and traders may capture speculative gains through storage and timing of sales, provided there is adequate facilities.

3.7 Comparing Katsina state price movement 2023 and 2024

The maize price data across the Katsina state market showed parallel inflationary patterns to those observed in Kaduna, with distinct regional characteristics. There was an annual average price increasing of about 103.7 - 106.2% between 2023 and 2024. The Bakori

market showed rising from ₦327.20/kg to ₦666.53/kg (about 103.7% increase), while Dandume market showed the highest price level in 2024 at ₦679.70/kg which exceed annual variability suggesting a structural changes in the maize business.

The graphical representation (Figure 3) clearly showed a rise in the 2024 price curve maintaining a consistently elevated position throughout the annual cycle. Funtua market which was the highest in 2023 average at ₦353.94/kg, was surpassed by Dandume market in 2024 (₦679.70/kg vis-a-vis ₦672.51/kg). Tsiga market maintained small increase in both years, with an average of ₦653.42/kg in 2024 representing a 115.0% increase from 2023 levels. This position showed that while, inflationary pressures affected the markets in Katsina state uniformly, underlying factors determining inter-market price differential may be evolving.

Fig. 3: Result of Katsina State price movement 2023 vis-a-vis 2024

The 2023 result of analysis showed a smooth seasonal patten with June August peak, the 2024 showed more abrupt transitions and sustained high prices throughout the Preharvest season. The graphical representation highlights the traditional postharvest price decline but in 2024 the October - December prices stabilized at nearly double the price in the previous year 2023. This stabilization at elevated prices indicated underlying demand pressures and reduced effectiveness of traditional seasonal risk management strategies (Relief Web, 2024; AFEX, 2024).

The deviation of annual average price across market increased from ₦19.38/kg in 2023 to ₦16.41/kg in 2024, indicating relatively stable market dispersion despite overall inflation. There was however, periods of divergence, particularly during the May to August Preharvest season, when price spreads between markets temporarily widened. This can be attributed to transportation bottlenecks and localized supply shocks that may have periodically disrupted market integration during some period. This altered seasonal pattern may disrupt traditional storage based livelihood strategies.

Katsina revealed some similarity and differences with Kaduna state findings, while both state experienced close percentage price increases, but katsina market showed slightly lower price levels, more stable inter-market relationships and less pronounced Preharvest season spikes. This could be due to alternative transportation routes to surplus regions.

4.0 Price Volatility

4.1 Analysis of Price Volatility in Kaduna and Katsina Maize Markets (2023-2024)

The result for price volatility across the selected markets in Kaduna and Katsina state was presented in

Table 6. The result showed some level of stability between the two years under inflationary pressure. The result shows a reduction in price within the selected markets which was evident by the declined in coefficients of variations value between 2023 and 2024. For the Kaduna state there was a decline from (30 – 40) % in 2023 to (20 – 25) % in 2024, this represents an average reduction of 11 percent points. The Katsina market result showed similar pattern with coefficients of variation declining from (23 – 36) % to (17 – 22) %. These shows stabilization despite higher price levels in 2024 which could be as a result of shifts in market dynamics. This pattern aligns with findings by Sani and Abu (2022) who found that while maize prices in Nigeria are generally volatile, volatility tends to moderate over time when structural factors such as storage, market information and policy interventions are improved.

Tudun Saibu in Kaduna showed the highest volatility in 2023 with correlation of variation of 40%, while Tsigas in Katsina state showed stability in both year of 29% in 2023 and 17% in 2024. Funtua market showed significant volatility reductions, from 23% to 22%, while maintaining its position as one of the most stable major markets in the region. These may be due to market size, trader concentration, and transportation connectivity.

The relationship between average prices level and volatility showed that while prices more than doubled in all markets, standard deviations increased by only a range of (25 – 40)% resulting in lower coefficient of variations. This result suggests that, as price reach higher levels, percentage fluctuations become relatively smaller as shown in Figure 4.

Table 6

Result of degree of Price Instability in Kaduna & Katsina States 2023 vis-à-vis 2024

State	Market	Mean		StDev.		CV (%)	
		2023	2024	2023	2024	2023	2024
1. Kaduna	Anchau	330.67	675.26	115.25	145.92	35%	22%
	Makarfi	334.80	699.25	110.40	138.82	33%	20%
	Tudun Saibu	312.82	652.49	126.67	139.48	40%	21%
	Ikara	306.15	697.04	91.60	171.76	30%	25%
	Giwa	331.04	648.97	106.25	148.69	32%	23%
	Saminaka	298.07	611.88	102.44	128.32	34%	21%
	Pambegua	301.66	618.00	98.65	128.50	33%	21%
2. Katsina	Bakori	327.20	666.53	117.90	146.29	36%	22%
	Dandume	329.65	679.70	99.67	135.73	30%	20%
	Jabiri (Funtua)	353.94	672.51	83.01	147.09	23%	22%
	Faskari	340.30	636.89	101.33	137.72	30%	22%
	Tsiga	303.93	653.42	89.11	113.18	29%	17%

Source: Survey Data, 2025

Katsina state markets generally showed lower volatility than the markets in Kaduna state for the both years (2023 and 2024) the average coefficient of variations across Katsina state markets was 30% in 2023

compared to Kaduna state markets which was 33%, and this difference was 21% and 22% in 2024 for Katsina and Kaduna States respectively.

Fig. 4: Result of degree of Price Instability in Kaduna and Katsina state 2023 vis-à-vis 2024

The differences may be due to the presence of more developed market infrastructure and integration with surplus producing regions. The study by Uduji, Okolo-Obasi, and Asongu (2020) found that programs like the Growth Enhancement Support Scheme (GESS) can help reduce food price volatility through better input and market information provision. The result showed smaller fluctuations despite the larger increase in prices in 2024. This may be as the result of market participants (Farmers and traders) adapting to the new price regime through modified storage strategies and trading behaviours, increase use of price information systems or improved storage technologies.

5.0 Conclusion and Policy Recommendations

This research shows an inflationary pressure with prices increasing more than double in both Kaduna and Katsina States. Despite the increase however, the volatility levels which was measured by the coefficients of variation declined from between (30 – 40) % in 2023 to (20 – 25) % in 2024 for Kaduna state and from (23 -36) % to (17 – 22) % in Katsina state. This showed that the maize markets operated under substantial inflationary pressure which could be due to supply shocks and inadequate infrastructures like road, mechanized production and the rest but there was stability at a high price maintained for the period. Possibly through storage, arbitrage and information flows within the market. The persistent high prices threaten household food security, especially for vulnerable rural population.

Investments in rural roads, storage facilities such as supporting farmers, cooperatives and traders to adopt modern storage techniques (hermetic) and expansion of warehouse receipt system, and logistics will reduce transaction cost and reduce offseason price increase, inter market differentials and improved infrastructure are critical to addressing price increase in market such as Tudun saibu (Kaduna) and Bakori (Katsina). There is need for input support schemes to assist in reducing

production cost and ease the inflationary pressures and its effects on poor households and regional trade and market integration between state agricultural agencies. Federal and trade linkages between surplus and deficit regions also cross border trade within the Economic Community of West African States (ECOWAS) to buffer domestic supply shocks within the ECOWAS state is recommended.

Conflict of Interest

No known conflict of interest exists for any author.

References

1. Abate, G.T., Rashid, S., Borzaga, C., & Getnet, K. (2016) Rural Finance and Agricultural Technology Adoption in Ethiopia: Does the Institutional Design of Lending Organizations Matter? *World Development*, 84, 235-253. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.worlddev.2016.03.003>
2. Abdulai, A. (2000). Spatial price transmission and asymmetry in the Ghanaian maize market. *Journal of Development Economics*, 63(2), 327–349. [https://doi.org/10.1016/S0304-3878\(00\)00115-2](https://doi.org/10.1016/S0304-3878(00)00115-2)
3. AFEX. (2024, January 25). AFEX predicts higher prices for maize, rice in Nigeria 2024. Milling: Grain Middle East and Africa. Retrieved from <https://millingmea.com/afex-predicts-higher-prices-for-maize-rice-in-nigeria-2024/>
4. Federal Ministry of Agriculture and Rural Development (FMARD). (2011). *Agricultural Transformation Agenda: A blueprint for transformation of agriculture in Nigeria*.
5. Agricultural Transformation Agenda (ATA). Retrieved from <https://funaab.edu.ng/wp-content/uploads/2012/10/Agricultural%20Transformation%20Blue%20Print.pdf>

6. Gilbert, C.L., Christiaensen, L., & Kaminski, J. (2017). Food price seasonality in Africa: Measurement and extent. *Food Policy*, 67, 119–132. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.foodpol.2016.09.016>
7. Liverpool-Tasie, L.S.O., Omonona, B. T., Sanou, A., & Ogunleye, W. (2017). Is increasing inorganic fertilizer use for maize production in SSA a profitable proposition? Evidence from Nigeria. *Food Policy*, 91, 101836 <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.foodpol.2016.09.011>
8. Oyewole, S.N., Olayemi, F.F., Gbabe, E.K., Ogunbiyi, O.A., & Peters, O. (2018). Development and promotional challenges of inert atmosphere silo for grain storage in Nigeria. Proc. of the 12th CIGR Section VI International Symposium (2018).
9. Retrieved from ResearchGate: https://www.researchgate.net/publication/372189350_Development_and_Promotional_Challenges_of_Inert_Atmosphere_Silo_for_Grain_Storage_in_Nigeria
10. Relief Web. (2024). Nigeria Key Message Update May 2024: Atypical staple prices and below-average dry harvest-led high food assistance needs. ReliefWeb. <https://reliefweb.int/report/nigeria/nigeria-key-message-update-may-2024-atypical-staple-prices-and-below-average-dry-harvest-led-high-food-assistance-needs-2024/>
11. Sani, H., & Abu, O. (2022). Evaluating maize price volatility and its implication for food security in Nigeria. *Nigerian Journal of Agriculture and Agricultural Technology*, 2(1), 1-8. <https://doi.org/10.59331/njaat.v2i1.2>
12. Uduji, J.I., Okolo-Obasi, E.N., & Asongu, S.A. (2020). Analysis of Farmers' Food Price Volatility and Nigeria's Growth Enhancement Support Scheme. African Governance and Development Institute Working Paper. <http://mpira.ub.uni-muenchen.de/107241/>
13. World Bank. (2014). Nigeria Agricultural Transformation Development Policy Operation (DPO document). Retrieved from <https://documents1.worldbank.org/curated/en/108471473086844801/pdf/Nigeria-Agricultural-Transformation-DPO.pdf>
14. Wossen, T., Menkir, A., Alene, A., Abdoulaye, T., Ajala, S., Badu-Apraku, B., Gedil, M., Mengesha, W., & Meseke, S. (2023). Drivers of transformation of the maize sector in Nigeria. *Global Food Security*, 38, 100713. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.gfs.2023.100713>
15. Zalkuwi, J.W., Joshua, T., Faci, R.M., & Kayam, A. (2024). Maize and rice prices instability in Northeast, Nigeria. *International Journal of Humanities Social Science and Management*, 4(5), 308–319. Retrieved from https://ijhssm.org/issue_dcp/Maize%20and%20Rice%20Prices%20Instability%20in%20Northeast%2C%20Nigeria..pdf